

NATIONAL GAMES GLORIFY THE NATION

Amrullayeva Maxliyo Abdurahmonovna

Tashkent Academic Lyceum No.2 of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the
Republic of Uzbekistan.

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Abstract:

This article briefly shows the origin and development of national action games. Thanks to independence, wide prospects are opening up in the field of physical education and sports, especially physical education classes held on national games and exercises, sports. They are constantly and regularly taught to students application is giving good results, serving as an important factor in raising young people to be healthy, energetic, agile and strong will come. In this process, there is a wider way to implement the Uzbek folk action games inherited from our history. to be revealed, to publicize it, to organize it in the family, preschool education and holidays, the growing has a positive effect on youth education. Key words: Folk games, horse racing, Alpomish, Chillak, ancient times, fencing, javelin.

Abstract: This article briefly shows how national action games were created and developed. Thanks to independence, wide prospects are opening up in the field of physical education and sports, especially the national games and exercises of the people, and physical education classes held in sports. Their constant and regular application to students gives good results, it serves as an important factor in raising young people to be healthy, energetic, agile and strong. opening a wider way to its implementation, publicizing it, organizing it in the family, preschool education and holidays, has a positive effect on the education of the growing youth.

The history of the development of any ethnic group, large or small nation, first of all, the traditions of folk education means to know the essence. Northern peoples have been unique in terms of content, forms and methods since ancient times formed the system of folk pedagogy. With the adoption of the national concept, the student it is taken into account that it is possible to achieve lateral development with the help of national sports, exercises, and games. In modern society, national sports, national physical exercises and games of the people of Sakhalin are physical education and developed further as a separate direction in the general system of sports. Folk traditions of our multi-ethnic region is becoming a model of rapid development and improvement. National sports and folk games are common to our people is an integral part of culture. Finding,

collecting and summarizing the rare masterpieces of national folk games and counting terms putting it into practice is one of the necessary tasks in restoring our abilities and spirituality. People are national action games not only give pleasure to children in their own way, but also respect our spiritual wealth teaches to look at, respect and preserve them. National folk action games are from ancient times Since then, it has been widely used in contests and competitions as an independent field in folk rituals and traditions. Physical education has developed over thousands of years, formed in the customs, traditions and customs of the people. National games of the people have reached us for thousands of years. Uzbek national folk games "Riding on a horse", "Chasing a girl", "Capricorn", "Archery", "Chillak", "White bone", "Soqqa", "Five stones" and through other games, in developing the qualities of bravery, dexterity, quickness, and maintaining balance, as well as in the formation of stature, morals, mind, memory, attention, and of course, in improving health has been the most effective means of strengthening. National sports, games, exercises as a practical sport for engaging in other sports is used. Various games for speed, strength, dexterity and endurance have always been popular among peoples. In my opinion, national sports should be mandatory in the curriculum of physical education in higher education. They are very has great educational, health care and general educational value. National sports, exercises and games educational importance is very great. The people who invented these types are always proud of their modesty, good manners and were distinguished by their hospitality. National sports educate moral and willful qualities. National sports, exercises and games are fast-paced develops qualities, speed endurance. The history of the development of any ethnic group, large or small nation, first of all, the traditions of folk education means to know the essence.

It is known that the physical condition and level of physical fitness of the population living in different regions of our country and physical indicators. It includes physical education classes and national open games because it is diverse in nature, it is studied taking into account the individual characteristics of children and related to the development of developed motor skills and abilities. These are all modern methods allows finding a "golden mean" between the standards and traditions of different nations. Our ancestors are not only us to become physically mature in all aspects, but also spiritually stable, morally and aesthetically enriched created unusual, colorful sports, as well as physical exercises that help. In conclusion, the inclusion of national outdoor games in physical education lessons is not only a part of ethnopedagogy part, but also the

all-round physical development of the child, not only his own people, but also the peoples of different countries it also ensures close acquaintance with the culture

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